

A 2D Explicit-Reflector For SP_N And S_N Pin-by-pin Multigroup Calculations

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ABSTRACT

EDF/Framatome are currently developing a state-of-the-art calculation chain called ODYSSEE. This chain includes Best-Estimate calculations based on multigroup pin-wise SP_N or S_N calculations, aimed at providing references for reactors calculation. This paper focuses on analyzing the accuracy and robustness of a 2D multigroup reflector model for multigroup pin-by-pin SP_N and S_N calculations. For the core fuel assemblies, a SPH-equivalence is applied to preserve reaction rates, while for the radial reflector medium, a 2D Explicit-Reflector model is employed. This model is based on a 2D homogenized and collapsed reflector medium, computed from a 2D core reference transport calculation using the EDF/Framatome code CARABAS, which incorporates the CEA APOLLO2 code.

The validation cases consist of 2D static and depletion calculations on the KAIST core benchmark, enriched with various fuel loading patterns and associated with either a water or steel reflector. First, the reference CARABAS core calculations are compared with Monte Carlo results. Then, the accuracy and loading-pattern robustness of the 2D Explicit-Reflector are analyzed. Pin-by-pin SP₃ and S₈ calculations with 8 and 36 energy groups are compared to the CARABAS reference results. Finally, depletion multigroup SP₃ and S₈ calculations are performed. The observed discrepancies confirm the high accuracy and robustness of the 2D Explicit-Reflector with respect to core layout and fuel burnup, regardless of whether the reflector is made of steel or water.

Keywords: Reflector, SP_N, S_N

1. INTRODUCTION

Over the past few years, EDF/Framatome R&D has developed a new state-of-the-art computational chains, ODYSSEE [1, 2] which is set to replace the current chain CASSIOPEE and SCIENCE V2.

While ODYSSEE relies on diffusion calculations for industrial applications, it also incorporates Best-Estimate multigroup schemes designed to closely match the accuracy of reference transport calculations. These Best-Estimate methods require less memory and computational time than full transport calculations, thereby enabling the simulation of reactor depletion across the EDF fleet.

Best-Estimate calculations [3] based on pin-by-pin multigroup S_N or SP_N methods require a multigroup reflector model. This article focuses on a 2D Explicit-Reflector modelling and analyzes its accuracy and robustness with respect to core loading patterns and depletion calculations.

In Section 2, Best-Estimate multigroup calculations are briefly described, and the 2D Explicit-Reflector cross-sections computation is explained.

In Section 3, we present the validation cases which consist of various core layouts for the core benchmark KAIST associated with either a water or a steel reflector medium. The discrepancies between reference CARABAS [2] calculations and Monte-Carlo ones, which were performed with the CEA code TRIPOLI 4.12 [4] are given.

Finally, in Section 4, the accuracy of the 2D Explicit-Reflector and its loading-pattern robustness are analysed. Pin-by-pin SP₃ or S₈ calculations with 8 or 36 energy-groups are compared to the CARABAS

reference calculations on the various KAIST benchmark configurations. Additionally, depletion pin-by-pin SP_3 calculations with 8 or 36 energy groups are performed and compared with EDF/Framatome code CARABAS depletion calculations.

2. A 2D EXPLICIT-REFLECTOR MODEL FOR PIN-BY-PIN MULTIGROUP SP_N AND S_N CALCULATIONS

2.1. EDF/Framatome R&D Best-Estimate multigroup SP_N and S_N calculations

Pin-by-pin multigroup Best-Estimate calculations are based on a classical 2-step approach.

The first step involves generating few-group cross-section libraries using assembly reference transport calculations performed with the EDF/Framatome code CARABAS. The resulting pin-cell homogenized multigroup (up to 36) cross-sections are then used as input for multigroup core calculations. For pin-by-pin calculations, the fuel assembly library is enhanced with SPH-equivalence [5] coefficients aiming at preserving the reaction rates for the assembly in an infinite medium.

The second step consists of Best-Estimate core calculations, which rely on either a Simplified P_N solver (referred to as the SP_N solver) described in [5] or a Discrete Ordinates solver (referred to as the S_N solver) described in [6].

2.2. Reference CARABAS Transport Core Calculations

This section presents the 2D reference transport calculations used to compute the 2D radial Explicit-Reflector cross-sections.

The CARABAS core reference transport calculations are performed using the deterministic CEA transport code APOLLO2 [7] and rely on a two-step core flux calculation.

In the first step, cross-sections for each fuel assembly are self-shielded using the Livolant Jean-Pierre methodology. For non-peripheral fuel assemblies, self-shielding is performed on the assembly with reflective boundaries conditions. For peripheral fuel assemblies, self-shielding is carried out on the assembly within an surrounding environment. For reflector media, the self-shielding is performed on a slab containing the fuel assembly and the reflector media. These self-shielded cross-sections are then used as an input for a 281-energy-group multi-cell collision probability calculation (P_{ij}) applied to the same configurations used for the self-shielding.

The second step involves computing one-eighth (or one quarter) of the core using the Linear Surfacic Method Of Characteristics (MOC), based on the previous generated 281-group cross-sections collapsed into 36 energy groups.

For CARABAS reference depletion calculations, the water and fuel temperatures, water density, and boron concentration are fixed. Only the fuel isotopic concentrations evolve over time. The 281-group flux solution of the core k_{eff} calculation—obtained by convoluting the 36-group MOC flux with the 281-group P_{ij} flux—is used as an input to the Bateman depletion equations. The isotopic chain consists of about 160 isotopes.

2.3. 2D Explicit-Reflector cross-sections computation

The 2D Explicit-Reflector model is based on the assumption that multigroup pin-by-pin SP_N and S_N calculations can handle homogenized few energy-group cross-sections without requiring equivalence cross-section corrections when the media involved are not too heterogenous.

Thus, the 2D Explicit-Reflector cross-sections are directly derived from the homogenization and the energy-group collapsing of the reference transport CARABAS calculation.

Figure 1. 2D Explicit-Reflector cross-sections computation methodology

Therefore, for a given core layout, a CARABAS core reference calculation is performed. Next, the 36-group reflector cross-sections are collapsed into a few energy groups and homogenized on a Cartesian pin-wise mesh using the 36-group reference MOC flux. The resulting pin-wise multigroup reflector cross-sections are then stored in a neutronic reflector assembly library. The addition of a pin-wise mesh to the MOC calculation mesh has been automated for any reactor within the CARABAS code. In Figure 1, the MOC mesh in the reflector area is not represented.

Since reflector cross-sections depend on boron concentration and water density, several 2D core calculations with varying densities and boron concentrations are required to have multi-parameters feedback reflector libraries. Regarding the core layouts, as it will be shown in Section 4, the 2D Explicit-Reflector cross-sections appear to be largely independent of them. Therefore, only one radial reflector library needs to be computed for each reactor type.

3. VALIDATION METHODOLOGY

3.1. Enriched KAIST 1A and 1B benchmark

The KAIST benchmark problem, first introduced in [8], models a small 900 MWth PWR reactor of 52 assemblies with MOX fuel. It has been extended in [9] to include additional reflector materials. In our study, we use the *standard light water reflector* (designated by the number 1) and the *steel reflector with water holes* (variant 2, designated by the number 2). Their geometries are presented in Figure 2 and their material compositions are detailed in [9].

Figure 2. KAIST light water and steel medium reflectors

To test the dependency of reflector cross-sections on the fuel core layout, two additional configurations—named B and C—were introduced, each using fuel assemblies at zero burnup. These configurations are shown in Figure 3. The UOX assembly enriched to 1.5% in ^{235}U has the same geometry as the UOX assembly enriched to 2.0%. The only difference lies in the ^{235}U enrichment level. Configurations A, B and C share identical core conditions: $T_{water} = 570\text{ K}$, $T_{fuel} = 900\text{ K}$ and $\rho = 0.7295\text{ g/cm}^3$, with a boron concentration of 800 ppm. In this article, a configuration referred to as “2B” denotes a loading pattern B combined with reflector type “2”, i.e., the steel reflector.

Figure 3. KAIST different layouts A, B and C

Additionally, reference Monte-Carlo calculations were performed using the CEA code TRIPOLI 4.12 to validate the CARABAS reference results. The estimated uncertainty on k_{eff} was below 1 pcm, and the pin-wise one-group flux uncertainty was less than $7 \times 10^{-4} \%$. The discrepancies in k_{eff} and one-group flux distributions between CARABAS and TRIPOLI 4.12, for the 1A and 2A configurations, are presented in Table 4.

Figure 4. Comparison on the one-group flux between CARABAS and reference TRIPOLI 4.12 results

CARABAS and TRIPOLI 4.12 calculations show good consistency, with one-group flux discrepancies remaining low ($\leq 2\%$) across the main core region for both 1A and 2A configurations. Larger discrepancies are observed at the assembly corners adjacent to the reflector, particularly in the case of the light water reflector. These higher corner errors may be attributed to the self-shielding and P_{ij} calculation step. The simplified averaged reflector environment used for self-shielding and the P_{ij} calculation of the peripheral fuel assemblies appears to be less suitable for diagonal assemblies than for those located along the X or Y axes.

4. RESULTS

This section focuses on evaluating the dependency of the 2D Explicit-Reflector on core loading pattern and fuel burnup.

4.1. SP_N and S_N calculations options

For the fuel assemblies, SP_N and S_N calculations rely on pin-by-pin cross-section libraries generated using the CARABAS assembly scheme (see [1]). These output libraries can be collapsed into a reduced-group library using flux as a weighting function. They contain only P1 scattering cross-sections, meaning the scattering cross-section is expanded in Legendre polynomials up to first order. These libraries are then enriched with pin-by-pin multi-group equivalence factors obtained from an SPH procedure applied to each assembly under symmetry boundary conditions.

For the reflector medium, the calculation scheme described in Section 2 is used. Reflector libraries contain pin-by-pin cross-sections for a few energy groups, along with P3 scattering cross-sections to account for reflector anisotropy.

To ensure good spatial convergency, pin-by-pin SP_3 calculations use RT1 Raviart Thomas polynomials, while pin-by-pin S_8 calculations employ a diamond-scheme of order 0 with a 2x2 pin refinement in the computational mesh (see [3]).

4.2. Robustness of the 2D Explicit-Reflector from the core layout

In this section, the steel and light water 2D Explicit-Reflectors are computed using layout A with the following feedback axes: boron-10 concentration values of 0 ppm, 1000 ppm, 2000 ppm, and water densities of 0.7 g/cm^3 and 0.8 g/cm^3 . One can note that the reflector libraries do not include a feedback axis for core fuel burnup.

For each core layout—A, B, and C—pin-by-pin SP_3 and S_8 calculations are performed using 8 and 36 energy groups, for both the steel and light water reflector cases. Table I presents the discrepancies in k_{eff} and pin-wise fission rates compared to the CARABAS reference calculations for the light water reflector, while Table II shows the corresponding results for the steel reflector.

Although core layouts B and C differ from layout A—used for computing the 2D Explicit-Reflector cross-sections—for the peripheral assemblies, the relative errors in S_8 and SP_3 calculations remain low and consistent across all three layouts, regardless of the reflector material. This demonstrates the limited dependency of the 2D Explicit-Reflector on the loading pattern.

Additionally, the 8-group results are quite close to the 36-group results for both S_8 and SP_3 calculations. The accuracy of the 36-group S_8 calculations is slightly lower than that of the 8-group or 36-group SP_3 results, particularly in the steel reflector configurations.

Figures 6 and 5 show the spatial distribution of the discrepancies. It can be observed that the higher discrepancies in S_8 calculations occur in the peripheral assemblies, even in configuration A. The SPH equivalence correction in S_N may be more sensitive to the surrounding spectral environment than the one used in SP_N equations, which could explain the improved accuracy of SP_N calculations.

4.3. Accuracy of the 2D Explicit-Reflector according to the core burnup

This section presents depletion pin-by-pin SP_3 calculations using 8 and 36 energy groups on the KAIST layouts 1A and 2B. During depletion, the boron concentration, water density, and fuel and moderator temperatures are kept constant. The multigroup SP_3 results are compared to the CARABAS reference depletion calculations. The objective is to verify whether the observations made for static, zero-burnup calculations remain valid under depletion conditions. While the COCAGNE SP_N calculation evolution

Table I. Water 2D Explicit-Reflector calculations

Core config	refKeff	Calculation	8-group calculation				36-group calculation			
			err k_{eff} pcm	min (%)	max (%)	RMS (%)	err k_{eff} pcm	min (%)	max (%)	RMS (%)
Config 1A	1.13079	SP_3-P_3	-5	-1.1	1.9	0.5	109	-1.2	0.8	0.4
		S_8-P_3	1	-1.4	1.8	0.6	114	-1.2	1.0	0.5
Config 1B	1.12994	SP_3-P_3	-8	-1.2	2.5	0.6	107	-1.2	1.0	0.4
		S_8-P_3	-1	-1.4	2.4	0.7	112	-1.2	1.1	0.5
Config 1C	1.12628	SP_3-P_3	9	-1.2	2.5	0.6	107	-1.2	1.0	0.4
		S_8-P_3	2	-1.5	2.4	0.7	112	-1.2	1.1	0.5

Table II. Steel 2D Explicit-Reflector calculations

Core config	refKeff	Calculation	8-group calculation				36-group calculation			
			err k_{eff} pcm	min (%)	max (%)	RMS (%)	err k_{eff} pcm	min (%)	max (%)	RMS (%)
Config 2A	1.13348	SP_3-P_3	-13	-1.2	3.2	0.5	106	-1.1	2.5	0.4
		S_8-P_3	7	-1.2	4.6	1.0	125	-1.4	3.6	1.0
Config 2B	1.13281	SP_3-P_3	-17	-1.7	3.3	0.7	103	-1.1	2.4	0.4
		S_8-P_3	3	-1.3	4.3	1.0	123	-1.4	3.6	0.9
Config 2C	1.12810	SP_3-P_3	7	-1.3	3.0	0.6	106	-1.1	2.2	0.4
		S_8-P_3	5	-1.2	4.3	1.0	119	-1.3	3.7	0.9

 Figure 5. SP_3 and S_8 discrepancies with CARABAS on pin fission rates (1A configuration)

Figure 6. SP_3 and S_8 discrepancies with CARABAS on pin fission rates (2A configuration)

chains include approximately 40 isotopes, the CARABAS depletion chain consists of around 160 isotopes. Figure 7 shows the evolution of k_{eff} and the discrepancies (minimum, maximum, and RMS) in the pin-wise relative power error for both the steel and light water reflector cases.

(a) 1A configuration (light water reflector)

(b) 2A configuration (steel reflector with water holes)

Figure 7. Depletion comparisons between multigroup SP_3 and reference CARABAS transport calculations

We observe that discrepancies in k_{eff} and pin-wise power distribution remain stable throughout core burnup for both 8-group and 36-group SP_3 calculations, even during the gadolinium depletion peak. These discrepancies are very small, with an RMS error in pin power below 0.8% and a k_{eff} error under 100 pcm. These results confirm the robustness of the 2D Explicit-Reflector with respect to core layout burnup, as well as the effectiveness of the carefully selected reduced isotopic depletion chain.

5. CONCLUSION

The comparisons between Best-Estimate SP_N and S_N calculations and reference CARABAS transport calculations performed in this study demonstrate the high accuracy and robustness of pin-by-pin multi-group SP_N and S_N schemes when combined with the 2D Explicit-Reflector modelling. The 2D Explicit-Reflector cross-sections have shown minimal sensitivity to both core burnup and core loading patterns variations.

In the future, improvements in SPH-equivalence computation within heterogeneous environments may further enhance the accuracy of Best-Estimate calculations.

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REFERENCES

- [1] P.M. Demy, V. Bouhours, C. Lafaurie, A. Marquis, M. Paradis, S. Ravaux, C. Rechatin, C. Aulagnier, B. Garneret, D. Kerdraon, N. Hfaiedh, E. Noblat, N. Schwarz, P.V. Marquet, V. Duffal, S. Pujet. "Physical Validation of ODYSSEE Nuclear Code System." *PHYSOR 2026*.
- [2] E. Martinolli, D. Raynaud, C.Rechatin, C. Lafaurie, G. Vandermoere, D. Couyras, N. Schwartz, N. Zaremba, P. Duval-Pineau, S. Pujet, E. Le Coupanec, C. Aulagnier, T. Courau, D. Kerdraon. "ODYSSEE, the new EDF and Framatome Nuclear Code System." *PHYSOR 2026*.
- [3] A. Willien, R. Delvaux, N. Guler, D. Raynaud. "Neutronic Best-Estimate Simulation with the New EDF and Framatome ODYSSEE Platform: Application on EPR Flamanville 3 Design." *PHYSOR 2026*.
- [4] A. Zoia and al. "Overview of the TRIPOLI-4 Monte Carlo Code, Version 12." *EPJ Nuclear Sci Technol*.
- [5] M. Fliscounakis, E. Girardi, T. Courau, and D. Couyras. "Potential of Pin-By-Pin SPN Calculations as an Industrial Reference." *ICAPP 2012* (April 2012).
- [6] S. Moustafa, I. Dutka-Malen, L. Plagne, A. Ponçot, P.Ramet. "Shared memory parallelism for 3D Cartesian discrete ordinate solver." *Annals of Nuclear Energy*, **volume 82**, pp. 179–187 (August 2015).
- [7] Sanchez and al. "APOLLO2 Year 2010." *Annals of Nuclear Energy* (2010).
- [8] N. Z. Cho. "KAIST Nuclear Reactor Analysis and Particule Yransport Laboratory, Benchmark Problem 1A." URL <https://github.com/nzcho/Nurapt-Archives>.
- [9] S. Santandrea and al. "CAMIVVER, Codes And Methods Improvements for VVER Comprehensive Safety Assessment." URL <http://camivver-h2020.eu/src/assets/doc/D4-6.pdf>.